

ASSESSMENT OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN CHHATRAPATI SAMBHAJI NAGAR DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Agriculture, contributing 18.3% to India's GDP in 2022-23, faces challenges like fragmented landholdings, water scarcity, and weather-related risks, making crop insurance vital. This study examines the socio-economic impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in managing agricultural risk, reducing financial losses, supporting livelihoods, and promoting modern practices. Since its launch in 2016, PMFBY has improved upon previous schemes but still faces issues like delayed compensation. The study focuses on Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar district, surveying 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers during the 2023 kharif season. Findings show insured farmers had better education, resources, and profitability, but challenges like compensation delays and insufficient coverage remain. Recommendations include timely payouts, greater transparency, and expanded coverage.

Keywords: PMFBY, progress, income stability constraints

Introduction

Agriculture contributes significantly to India's economy, making up 18.3% of its GDP, but faces constant risks from natural disasters like droughts, floods, and cyclones. To address these challenges, agricultural insurance acts as a critical safety net for farmers, helping them cope with losses and stabilize their income. By spreading the financial burden of crop losses over space and time, insurance promotes resilience and sustainable investments in agriculture.

India's crop insurance journey began in the 1960s with a model crop insurance scheme. Over the years, several initiatives, including the Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) in 1985 and Rashtriya Krishi Bima Yojana (RKBY) in 1999, were introduced to cover natural risks. The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), launched in 2016, further simplified premiums and expanded coverage, offering rates of 2% for Kharif crops and 1.5% for Rabi crops. PMFBY provides comprehensive coverage from pre-sowing to post-harvest, ensuring financial support to farmers facing crop losses due to natural calamities.

Technological integration is a key feature of PMFBY, using digital tools like mobile apps and satellite imagery for loss assessment. The National Crop Insurance Portal streamlines communication between stakeholders, improving efficiency. However, challenges remain, such as low awareness, delayed claim settlements, and unreliable assessments. PMFBY 2.0, introduced in 2020, made insurance voluntary for loanee farmers and introduced reforms to address these issues.

This study aims to evaluate the policy framework and implementation of PMFBY, focusing on its impact on farmers, insurance firms, and the government. It also explores how technological advancements can optimize crop assessment and insurance disbursements, enhancing the scheme's long-term sustainability. The research will highlight areas for improvement to further empower farmers and promote agricultural growth in India.

Several researchers, including Kumar & Phougat (2021) and Chadha & Srivastava (2022), have emphasized the importance of studying the evolution and adoption of crop insurance schemes (CIS). These works provide insights into the functioning of these schemes and the various changes they have undergone over time. Additionally, earlier studies, such as those by Varadan and Kumar (2012) and Aditya et al. (2018), have specifically focused on examining the impacts of CIS. They highlight the role of insurance as a financial cushion, helping farmers stabilize their income and protect themselves from agricultural risks. Similarly, Srinivasulu (2018) and Jamanal et al. (2019) have investigated the barriers that prevent farmers from accessing crop

insurance, emphasizing the need to improve the availability of such schemes as a safety net. Across the literature, there is a consensus that, despite implementation challenges, crop insurance schemes have overall been beneficial in supporting farmers financially, helping them manage risks and uncertainties, and providing a level of income security.

This article aims to examine the progress of PMFBY in Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar district, its impact on farmers' income stability, and the constraints in its implementation and suggestions thereof.

Materials And Methodology

A multistage purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the district, talukas, villages and sample farmers. Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar district was purposively selected for the study based on maximum number of insured farmers. From the selected Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar district, four talukas were chosen based on the progress of PMFBY. Three villages were selected from each taluka based on the scheme's progress. From each selected villages, 10 farmers insured under the scheme and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly selected. Thus, a total of 120 insured farmers and 120 non-insured farmers under PMFBY were chosen for the present investigation.

The survey method was adopted for data collection. To obtain the required primary data a pre-tested schedule was prepared to obtain data from the selected farmers through personal interviews. Both primary and secondary data were collected for the present investigation. Primary data were collected from 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers using a pre-tested schedule for the kharif season of 2023. Secondary data on the progress of PMFBY in the district were gathered from published sources (India stat, PMFBY websites) for the period from 2016 to 2023. ergth CAGR was employed to study the progress of PMFBY. The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated,

t = Time variable, b = Regression coefficient, a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the relationship.

$$\text{CAGR (r)} = [\text{Antilog (log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Impact of PMFBY on stability of farm income were estimated by using descriptive statistics.

Mean income = $\frac{\sum \text{income}}{N}$ Where

N is the number of observations.

Standard Deviation = $\sqrt{\frac{\sum(X-\text{Mean})^2}{N}}$

The standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion from the average income.

$CV = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$

This expresses the standard deviation as a percentage of the mean, indicating relative variability.

Income stability index = $1 - CV$

The Income stability Index was a metric used to assess the stability of income within a population or region.

Where:

CV is the coefficient of variation.

Finally, the study used Garrett's Ranking Technique to rank various factors based on their perceived importance or severity, often applied in surveys where respondents rank their preferences or concerns.

We converted the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

Percent Position = $\left(\frac{R_{ij}-0.5}{N_j}\right) \times 100$

Where

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th factor by the j th individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j th individual

We used Garrett's table to find the score corresponding to each percent position. The percentage position of each rank was converted into scores using Garrett's Table. For each factor, the scores from all individuals were summed up and then divided by the total number of farmers who provided scores. These average scores for each factor were then ranked in order and conclusions were drawn based on these rankings.

Results And Discussion

Progress of PMFBY

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers

India recorded a negative compound annual growth rate (CAGR) in farmer participation in the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) during both the *kharif* -7 per cent and *rabi* -2 per cent seasons, reflecting challenges in maintaining national insurance coverage. In contrast, Maharashtra showed positive trends, with the *kharif* season posting a 20 per cent CAGR, attributed to improved awareness and outreach efforts. The *rabi* season saw a modest 3 per cent growth. At the district level, Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar had mixed results: a 7 per cent increase in *kharif*, but a sharp -11 per cent decline in *rabi*, possibly due to region-specific challenges. These variations underscore the need for tailored policy interventions to improve farmer participation in agricultural insurance. The trends observed from 2016 to 2023 differ from earlier studies, such as Chanda and Srinivastav (2022), who reported a 4.40 per cent growth in insured farmers under the Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS). The results, statistically significant at the 5 per cent level, confirm real changes in insurance participation across regions and seasons.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area Insured

At the national level, the insured area under the PMFBY grew modestly with a 1 per cent CAGR during both *kharif* and *rabi* seasons, indicating stable but limited farmer engagement. Maharashtra, however, saw significant expansion, particularly in the *kharif* season with a 19 per cent CAGR, likely due to better outreach and policy alignment. The *rabi* season also recorded a moderate 4 per cent growth. In Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, the *kharif* season showed a modest 6 per cent CAGR, while the *rabi* season experienced a sharp -9 per cent decline, reflecting challenges such as lower perceived risk or financial constraints. These regional differences underscore the need for tailored interventions to improve insurance uptake, especially in areas like Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar where participation has dropped. In contrast to Chanda and Srivastava (2022), who reported a 1.94 per cent growth

under the WBCIS, this analysis highlights more pronounced regional disparities and seasonal declines.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported claims

Nationally, reported claims under PMFBY saw a sharp decline during the *kharif* season, with a positive CAGR of 8 per cent, possibly due to fewer adverse events or claim filing challenges. In contrast, *rabi* claims grew significantly by 44 per cent, suggesting increased risk exposure or better reporting mechanisms. In Maharashtra, *kharif* claims dropped sharply by -41 per cent, while *rabi* claims showed a slight 1 per cent increase, indicating a more stable situation during *rabi*. Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar displayed mixed trends: an -8 per cent decline in *kharif* claims and a steep -50 per cent drop in *rabi* claims, possibly due to fewer insured farmers or administrative issues. Overall, these variations in reported claims reflect region- and season-specific factors, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to improve the effectiveness of the PMFBY scheme. Kumara and Kumari (2020) reported positive growth rates reported claims

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved claims

Nationally, approved claims under PMFBY have declined significantly, with a -60 per cent CAGR in *kharif* and -26 per cent in *rabi*, suggesting stricter approval processes or improved agricultural practices. Maharashtra also saw a -42 per cent drop in *kharif* claims, though *rabi* claims slightly improved with a 3 per cent CAGR. In Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, *kharif* claims saw a modest -8 per cent decline, while *rabi* claims plummeted by -50 per cent, indicating challenges in the claims process. The overall decline highlights ongoing issues in claim approvals, especially in *rabi*, necessitating efforts to streamline compensation across regions and seasons.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid

Nationally, total claims paid under PMFBY have declined, with a -5 per cent CAGR in *kharif* and -20 per cent in *rabi*, possibly due to fewer insured events or improved risk management. In contrast, Maharashtra saw a 7 per cent increase in *kharif* claims paid, while *rabi* payments decreased by -13 per cent, indicating a reduction in disbursements. In Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, total claims paid declined by -8 per cent in *kharif* and a steep -49 per cent in *rabi*, reflecting fewer claims or processing challenges. These trends highlight regional disparities and suggest the need for improvements in the claims settlement process, especially during the *rabi* season.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmers benefited

Nationally, the number of farmers benefiting from PMFBY has declined, with a -6 per cent CAGR in *kharif* and -19 per cent in *rabi*, indicating reduced participation or challenges in accessing benefits. In Maharashtra, *kharif* saw slight growth with a 1% CAGR, while *rabi* mirrored the national decline at -19%. Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar had no growth in *kharif* beneficiaries 0 per cent but a drastic -58 per cent drop in *rabi*.

These declines highlight barriers to benefit access, especially in *rabi*, contrasting with Chanda and Srivastava's (2022) findings of positive growth under WBCIS. Addressing these issues is key to improving PMFBY's reach and effectiveness.

Gross income stability and income stability index of sample insured farmers

The table provides a comparative overview of gross yield metrics in scenarios with and without compensation. It includes essential statistics such as mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and income index. These metrics offer valuable insights into yield variability, average performance levels, and income efficiency across the two scenarios.

Standard Deviation

The standard deviation of gross yield decreased from ₹26,079.56 without compensation to ₹24,914.42 with compensation, indicating more stable yields. This reduction suggests that compensation helps reduce yield variability, providing farmers with greater consistency and financial security, which aids in better planning and resource management.

Mean

The mean gross yield increased from ₹159,271.67 without compensation to ₹177,598.94 with compensation, indicating that compensation enhances overall yield while reducing variability. This increase suggests a stronger financial safety net for farmers, enabling better risk management and promoting greater sustainability in farming practices.

Coefficient of variation (CV)

The coefficient of variation (CV) for gross yields decreased from 0.16 without compensation to 0.14 with compensation, indicating greater predictability and reduced relative fluctuations in yields. This consistency aids farmers in making informed decisions about resource allocation and future planning, underscoring compensation's role in enhancing yield reliability

Income stability index.

The income index increased from 0.83 for yields without compensation to 0.85 with compensation, indicating improved income generation efficiency and reduced risk exposure. Compensation also reduced yield variability, as evidenced by a lower standard deviation (₹24,914.42) and coefficient of variation (0.14) for gross yields with compensation. Additionally, the mean gross yield rose to ₹177,598.94 with compensation, highlighting its positive impact on productivity. Overall, compensation enhances agricultural productivity and financial stability, contributing to farmers' economic well-being by stabilizing yields and increasing average income efficiency.

The weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest its improvement

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers

The analysis highlights several critical constraints affecting the adoption and effectiveness of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). The most significant issue identified was insufficient compensation, with a mean score of 85, reflecting farmers' perceptions of inadequacy, which undermines their trust and satisfaction with the scheme. Closely following was the delay in realization of compensation (mean score of 78), indicating that slow payment processes contribute to financial strain and dissatisfaction among farmers. Additionally, the lack of qualified experts for assessing crop loss (mean score of 64) hinders efficient claim settlements, while insufficient coordination between banks and farmers (mean score of 63) leads to misunderstandings and processing delays. Other notable concerns included frequent changes in policy terms (mean score of 58), which create confusion during claims, and the need for timely claim disbursement before the next season (mean score of 45) to enable proper preparation for upcoming crops. Issues of corruption during assessment and settlement (mean score of 37) further erode trust, compounded by farmers' past negative experiences (mean score of 34) that make it hard to trust the scheme. Lastly, the lack of assurance for compensation after assessment (mean score of 29) underscores the uncertainty farmers face regarding the reliability of the PMFBY. Together, these constraints reveal the necessity for reforms to enhance the scheme's credibility and effectiveness, ensuring better support for farmers.

Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

To enhance the efficacy and acceptance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), it is crucial to address key constraints such as improving coordination, ensuring timely and adequate compensation, and tackling corruption and procedural complexities. This will significantly boost farmers' trust and satisfaction with the scheme. Insured farmers provided several suggestions for reform, with the most frequently mentioned being the need for timely compensation, emphasized by 76 farmers 63.33 per cent as a top priority. This underscores the critical importance of prompt financial relief for farmers' recovery and readiness for the next season.

Adequate compensation was the second most common suggestion, highlighted by 72 farmers 53.33 per cent, who expressed that current compensation levels are insufficient to cover their losses. Additionally,

61 farmers 50.83 per cent stressed the need for claims to be distributed before the start of the next season to ensure continuity in agricultural production. Transparency in the compensation process was also a key area for improvement, with 48 farmers 40 per cent calling for clearer communication from insurance agencies. Other notable suggestions included offering price guarantees 46 farmers, 38.33 per cent, establishing a uniform indemnity policy across regions and crops 43 farmers, 35.83 per cent, and improving agency operations 31 farmers, 25.8 per cent to streamline processes. Expanding the scheme to cover more crops was suggested by 39 farmers 32.5 per cent.

Suggestions for providing complete information on compensation 23 farmers, 19.17 per cent and improving awareness of the scheme 22 farmers, 18.33 per cent highlighted existing communication gaps. Overall, farmers emphasized the need for timely and adequate compensation, enhanced transparency, and improved agency operations. Addressing these issues will bolster trust in PMFBY, enhance its effectiveness, and promote greater adoption of crop insurance among farmers, ultimately providing stronger financial protection.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) reveals notable trends and challenges in its implementation. Nationally, insured farmers experienced a negative compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of -7 per cent in the *kharif* season and -2 per cent in *rabi*, indicating declining participation. In contrast, Maharashtra showed a positive trend, with a 20 per cent *kharif* CAGR and 3 per cent *rabi* growth due to improved outreach. Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar reported mixed results, with a 7 per cent increase in *kharif* but an 11 per cent decline in *rabi*. Nationally, the area insured grew modestly by 1 per cent for both seasons, while Maharashtra saw a significant 19 per cent *kharif* expansion and 4 per cent increase in *rabi*. Reported claims fell nationally by 8 per cent in *kharif* but surged by 44 per cent in *rabi*; Maharashtra faced a -41 per cent drop in claims with a slight *rabi* increase. Approved claims showed a -60 per cent CAGR in *kharif* and -26 per cent in *rabi* nationally, with Maharashtra experiencing a -42 per cent drop in claims. Total claims paid declined by -5 per cent in *kharif* and -20 per cent in *rabi* nationwide, while Maharashtra saw a 7 per cent increase in *kharif* claims paid. Participation fell nationally, with -6 per cent CAGR in *kharif* and -19 per cent in *rabi*. Gross income stability improved, indicated by a decrease in yield standard deviation from ₹26,079.56 to ₹24,914.42 and an increase in mean gross yield from ₹159,271.67 to ₹177,598.94. Key constraints included insufficient compensation (mean score of 85) and delays in realization (mean score of 78), along with a lack of qualified assessors and poor coordination with banks. Farmers suggested improvements such as timely compensation (emphasized by 63.33% of respondents), adequate compensation, transparency, price guarantees, and a uniform indemnity policy. Overall, the results highlight the complexity of PMFBY, indicating progress alongside critical areas needing attention to enhance effectiveness and farmer participation. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering trust and broader adoption of crop insurance among farmers

References

1. **Chadha D, Srivastava SK. 2022**, Crop Insurance: An economic review of its performance in India. *Biological Forum – An International Journal*. 2022; **14**(1): 434-439.
2. **Jamanal SK, Natikar KV, Potdar MP 2020**, . Constraints and suggestions expressed by the farmers in availing Crop Insurance Schemes in Northern Karnataka. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*. 2020; **32**(3): 1-5.
3. **Jiragal IM, Ganesamoorthi S, Mohankumar TL, Narayanswamy C. 2023**, Constraints and suggestions of beneficiary and non-beneficiary of farmers towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in Kolar district of Karnataka. *IAJES*. 2023; **41**(4): 55-61.

4. **Kumara SMK, Kumari DSS.2020**, Performance appraisal of PMFBY vis-à-vis RWBCIS in India. *J. Res. ANGRAU*. 2020; **47**(4): 1-11.
5. **Nagesh H, Rao BM, Krishna TG 2022**. Constraints faced by the beneficiaries of PMFBY and suggestions given by them to overcome the constraints in Srikakulam district of Andhra Pradesh. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. 2022; **41**(35): 40-43.
6. **Panigrahi SP, Nayak D, Meher M. Parasar B. (2019)**. Difficulties faced by the rice growers of Bhadrak district of Odisha for subscription of **Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojna (PMFBY)**. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2019; (5): 148-151
7. **Rawat A, Zechariah J. Study on impact of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) 2022** in Faridabad district of Haryana. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*.2022; **11**(4).
8. **Sharon M, Aparna B, Rajeswari S, Reddy RB 2023**. Impact of crop insurance schemes (PMFBY and WBCIS) on risk minimization in Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh, India. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. 2023; **12**(4): 2259-2263.
9. **Sheoran V, Kait R, Rani M, (2023)**. Assessing the effectiveness of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in Haryana. *IJESSM* .2023; **11**(3): 350

Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7%**
		t value	-1.98
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20%**
		t value	2.98
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR	7%**
		t value	1.73

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1%**
		t value	0.51
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19%**
		t value	1.34
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR	6%**
		t value	1.46

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8%
		t value	2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41%**
		t value	-1.52
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR	-8%**
		t value	-0.5

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60%**
		t value	-2.47
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42%**
		t value	-1.57
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR	-8%**
		t value	0.58

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5%**
		t value	-1.01
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7%**
		t value	0.83
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR	-8%**
		t value	0.56

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmer benefited under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR t value	-6%** -2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	1%** -0.73
3	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar	CAGR t value	0% -1.48

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 7: Income stability index of sample insured farmers from year 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Standard Deviation	26079.56	24914.42
Mean	159271.67	177598.94
Coefficient of Covariation	0.16	0.14
Income stability Index	0.83	0.85

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers (N=120) by Garretts ranking

Sr. no.	Constraints	Garrett's Mean	Garrett's Rank
1	Insufficient coordination of banks and farmers	63	IV
2	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY	82	I
3	Delay in realization of compensation	78	II
4	corruption while assessment and settling claims	24	X
5	Frequent change in policy terms or condition create confusion while claim settlement	58	V
6	Experts are unavailable for assessment of crop loss	64	III
7	Claim should be dispersed before starting of next season	45	VI
8	Hard to trust the scheme due to past experience	34	VIII
9	Even after assessment by agency there is no assurance of compensation	29	IX
10	PMFBY Portals should be updated to access the claim details	37	VII

Table 9 : Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Sr.no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Adequate Compensation	72	53.33	II
2	Timely Compensation	76	63.33	I
3	Transparency from Agencies	48	40.00	IV
4	Awareness of the Scheme	22	18.33	X
5	Complete Information on Compensation	23	19.17	IX
6	Improved Agency Operations	31	25.83	VIII
7	Uniform Indemnity for different regions and types of crops	43	35.83	VI
8	A greater number of crops are covered.	39	32.50	VII
9	Claims should be distributed before the start of the next season.	61	50.83	III
10	The insurance agency should offer insurance cover to include price guarantees.	46	38.33	V